

New Diagnosis Criteria for Common Variable Immunodeficiency Exploration Systematic Review and Current Perspectives

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Abstract:- Common variable immune deficiency (CVID) is the most common symptomatic immune deficiency in adults. It is defined by primary hypogammaglobulinemia with B-cells (CD19) present. It is a heterogeneous syndrome characterized clinically by recurrent bacterial infections (an almost constant feature), the frequency of autoimmune and/or granulomatous manifestations, and the presence of a lymphoproliferative syndrome (follicular hyperplasia, lymph nodes...). The seriousness of infections and their repetition should suggest the diagnosis, which will be confirmed by electrophoresis of the proteins and immunoglobulin tests. The treatment is based on regular substitution of polyvalent immunoglobulins, using intravenous or subcutaneous injection. The disease pathophysiology is poorly understood, but the immunological study of lymphocyte subpopulations, particularly B lymphocytes, and the recent description of certain genetic defects have improved our understanding. This study aims to cite the latest clinical and immunological characteristics of patients with CVID, as well as the genetic and pathogenic advances concerning this immune deficiency. In order to propose a new criteria to explore this pathology conducted to rule out other possible causes of hypogammaglobulinemia and differentials. Diagnoses using these criteria will enable patients with CVID to receive the best possible care.

Keywords:- CVID, Immunodeficiency, Hypogammaglobulinemia, B Cell.

I. INTRODUCTION

Common Variable Immunodeficiency Disorder (CVID) is the most common symptomatic primary immunodeficiency in adults. It is clinically characterized by recurrent severe infections, and/or autoimmunity and an increased risk of malignancy. Current studies estimate a prevalence of approximately 1 in 25,000 in the general population [1]. Significant ethnic variations exist and the frequency may be lower in some populations such as those in North-East Asia. Diagnosis is usually made in the second or third decade of life [2,3]. CVID is defined by significantly reduced IgG levels, usually associated, but variably, with decreased IgA and IgM levels. It is sometimes associated with impaired vaccine responses [4,5]. The blood lymphocyte populations phenotype is variable. The number of circulating B lymphocytes is either normal or decreased. Qualitative and quantitative abnormalities of T-cell immunity are observed in a fraction of patients. The genetic basis of these disorders has not been identified in the majority of individuals. It is now accepted that CVID is a polygenic syndrome. Rare patients with monogenic defects have been identified [6].

The objective of this article is to cite the latest clinical and immunological features of CVID, based on the latest immuno-phenotypic classification. It also aims to propose a strategy to explore this pathology, making it easier to rule out other causes of hypogammaglobulinemia and differentials. And finally, to take stock of the genetic and pathogenic advances concerning this immune deficiency.

II. CLINICAL SYMPTOMATOLOGY

The symptomatology of CVID is multifaceted, but recurrent respiratory tract and ENT infections are present in more than 90% of patients. A quarter of patients are also thought to have an autoimmune disease, most often autoimmune cytopenia, which may precede the diagnosis of immune deficiency by several years. Granulomatosis, particularly of the lungs or digestive tract, may also occur in some patients, leading to sarcoidosis-like symptoms.

Follicular lymphoid hyperplasia may develop, particularly in the lymph nodes, liver or spleen, and more rarely in the gastrointestinal tract. An increased risk of digestive and hematological cancers, has also been noted, and constitutes an important cause of death. CVID patients with at least one non-infectious complication have a higher morbidity/mortality than patients with only infectious complications [5,6].

➤ *Maintaining the Integrity of the Specifications*

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• *Diagnostic Approach to Hypogammaglobulinemia*

The key test for the diagnosis of any hypogammaglobulinemia is serum protein electrophoresis (figure 1), which is also the first step in the diagnosis of CVID. It is routinely the only relatively accurate quantitative test to assess overall gamma globulin concentration. This simple examination provides a great deal of information: it reveals hypo- (or hyper) gammaglobulinemia, the possible presence of a narrow immunoglobulin peak, and even other qualitative abnormalities;

This test also gives an accurate assessment of albuminemia, which is an important element in the etiological diagnosis of hypo-gammaglobulinemia. The protein profile often wrongly replaces the electrophoresis of proteins in routine. It provides by nephelometric analysis, a quantitative estimation of a large number of biological parameters (CRP, C3 and C4 fractions of the complement, orosomucoid, haptoglobin, albumin, IgG, IgA and IgM), but with insufficient precision concerning albuminemia and especially serum immunoglobulin concentrations. The diagnosis of hypo-gammaglobulinemia, is sometimes suspected on the presence of a decrease of one or more immunoglobulin fractions on the protein profile, and it should be confirmed by the serum protein electrophoresis.

The immunoglobulin and possibly the IgG subclass determinations (Tables 1 and 2) should be requested in order to clarify the characteristics of hypogammaglobulinemia, as the different Ig classes and IgG subclasses are variably

affected from patient to patient. To establish the diagnosis of hypogammaglobulinemia, serum protein electrophoresis should indicate a gamma globulin concentration below the lower limit of normal on at least two successive tests. This may vary depending on laboratories and is usually between 6 and 8 g/l in adults. (Figure 1)

• *Etiological Diagnosis of Hypogammaglobulinemia*

It should be noted that CVID diagnosis remains a diagnosis made by elimination, which would lead us to always rule out other causes of hypogammaglobulinemia before retaining an CVID (Table 3). A rigorous etiological approach is necessary to any hypogammaglobulinemia, which will be guided by the clinical context and standard hematological and biological examinations that will complete the request for serum protein electrophoresis (Table 1).

• *Hypogammaglobulinemia Associated to Hypoalbuminemia.*

If hypoalbuminemia is less than 30 g/l, it is important to look for protein leakage of renal origin (nephrotic syndrome) or less frequently of digestive origin (exudative enteropathy). However, etiologies where hypoalbuminemia is associated to hypogammaglobulinemia are not limited to extracorporeal protein leakage alone. Hypoalbuminemia may be observed transiently during an acute infectious episode. The association of hypogammaglobulinemia with transient hypoalbuminemia may also occur during the exceptional paroxysmal capillary hyperpermeability syndrome (acute episodes of severe collapse associated with hemoconcentration and hypoprotidemia/ hypoalbuminemia) [7].

In addition, chronic hypoalbuminemia may be indicative of a long-lasting inflammatory process or undernutrition in a patient who already has hypogammaglobulinemia. Hypoalbuminemia may also occur in certain forms of multiple myeloma and may indicate a poor prognosis in these forms. It is important to remember that some patients with CVID may also have permanent hypoalbuminemia, sometimes with no detectable cause (not explained by exudative enteropathy).

➤ *Hypogammaglobulinemia without Hypoalbuminemia:*

It falls mainly into two major etiological groups: primary immunodeficiencies (PIDs) and lymphoid hematological diseases.

• *Primary Immunodeficiencies (PIDs)*

✓ *Agammaglobulinemia*

In addition to CVID, other PIDs are associated or characterized by hypogammaglobulinemia. These are primarily agammaglobulinemia (Table 4) [8,9]. They are defined as serum gamma globulin concentrations of less than 1 g/l and an absence (or major decrease) in the number of circulating B-lymphocytes [10,11]. The most common form (90% of cases) is X-linked agammaglobulinemia (Bruton type) resulting from a mutation in the gene coding for btk, a member of the tyrosine kinase family [12]. Autosomal forms (10% of cases) are usually the result of mutations in genes

coding for one of the components of the pre-B receptor. The clinical picture is marked primarily by repeated neuro-meningeal, ENT, respiratory or digestive infections.

✓ *X-Linked Lymphoproliferation Syndrome (XLP or Purtilo Syndrome)*

In Purtilo syndrome, Male patients are generally healthy (although discrete abnormalities of immunity can be detected very early) until a primary infection with Epstein Barr Virus (EBV), resulting in a severe mononucleosis infection associated to hemophagocytosis, that can be fatal. Survivors usually develop deep hypogammaglobulinemia or non-Hodgkin's lymphoma type B. Recent studies have shown that mutations in the gene coding for the adaptor DSHP or SAP (signaling lymphocyte activating molecule associated protein) [13,14] can cause some cases of XLP.

✓ *Hyper-IgM Syndrome*

Hyper IgM syndrome results in normal or elevated serum polyclonal IgM (and IgD) concentrations, contrasting with a significant decrease in other classes of immunoglobulins, suggesting an isotypic switching defect. Levels of gamma globulins determined by serum protein electrophoresis are variable, decreased or normal, depending on IgM elevation. In the X-linked form there is a mutation in the gene coding for CD40 ligand (CD154) [15,16]. These patients develop infections of the respiratory tract, gastrointestinal tract, biliary tract and central nervous system, including atypical germs infections [15,16].

✓ *Other Primary Immunodeficiencies*

Hypogammaglobulinemia may occur in a variety of other DIPs: immunodeficiencies associated with growth hormone deficiency, ataxia telangiectasia (ATM gene mutation) [17], and various severe combined immunodeficiencies (SCID) whose clinical expression is usually dominated by a defect in cellular immunity [18,19]. In these patients, immunoglobulin production default can be masked in the first months of life, by maternal IgG.

• *Hypogammaglobulinemia Associated with Lymphoid Malignancies*

✓ *Example of Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia "CLL".*

In 20-25% of CLL cases, there is initially significant polyclonal hypogammaglobulinemia (<5 g/L) with or without monoclonal immunoglobulin [20,21]. Most often, it remains asymptomatic, but when levels are below 3 g/L and IgG levels below 2 g/L, recurrent infections, especially bronchopulmonary infections may occur, justifying therapeutic substitution with intravenous immunoglobulins.

Hypogammaglobulinemia may occur at the diagnosis of some non-Hodgkin's malignant lymphomas at a lower prevalence than in CLL.

In general, monoclonal immunoglobulin existence associated with a decrease in polyclonal fractions should lead to a search for lymphoid malignancy of the CLL type, non-Hodgkin's lymphoma or myeloma. However, in a not negligible number of patients with PIDs, especially CVID, a

monoclonal component may be observed. This situation justifies the search for malignant lymphoplasmacytic disease. CVID diagnosis should be retained based on age of onset, clinical picture and in the absence of any underlying malignant clonal lymphoproliferation. Nevertheless, surveillance is still necessary in these cases, so as not to ignore the possible emergence of hematological malignancy.

• *Transient Hypogammaglobulinemia*

During certain prolonged immunosuppressive treatments or as a result of cancer chemotherapy, hypogammaglobulinemia may occur. It is sometimes difficult to know whether it is a reflection of an unknown underlying immune deficiency revealed by the treatment or whether the deficiency is entirely induced by the therapy.

Some hypogammaglobulinemia, such as certain IgA deficiencies, can be induced in children, especially newborns, by various viral infections (CMV infection, measles, rubella, HIV...) [8]. Transient hypogammaglobulinemia, usually mild, may occur in infants. [9].

• *Good's Syndrome*

Good's syndrome (GS), or thymoma-associated immune deficiency, is a rare disease usually affecting adults between 40 and 70 years old. These patients typically have a thymoma associated to hypogammaglobulinemia, decreased or absent B cells, decreased T cells, an inverted CD4+ and CD8+ T cell ratio, and reduced T cell response to mitogen [22].

• *Diagnostic Criteria for CVID*

Various diagnostic criteria have been proposed. The definition published by the European Society for Immunodeficiency Diseases (ESID) and the Pan American Group for Immune Deficiency (PAGID) is commonly used [23,24]. The ESID/PAGID diagnostic criteria consist of three items (Table 5).

✓ (<http://esid.org/Working-Parties/Registry/Diagnosis-criteria,table5>)

However, these criteria have many limitations, for example, the first criterion, which requires immunoglobulin levels to be two standard deviations below the mean, can be met by 2.5% of the general population. In clinical practice, patients with slightly reduced IgG levels would rarely be studied [25,26].

➤ *Euroclass Classification*

In 2002, Europeans suggested a classification by flow cytometry in patients with CVID, according to the B cell phenotype [27,28]. This is the EUROclass trial, which involved a large cohort of patients with CVID from 8 European immunodeficiency centres. The objectives were to determine a clinical and immunological phenotype of the CVID patients in Europe and to improve and unify the classification scheme. The heterogeneity of common variable immunodeficiency (CVID) calls for a classification addressing pathogenic mechanisms as well as clinical relevance. This European multicenter trial was initiated to

develop a consensus of two existing classification schemes based on flow cytometric B cell phenotyping and the clinical course. The clinical evaluation of patients with the established diagnosis of CVID demonstrated a significant coincidence of granulomatous disease, autoimmune cytopenia, and splenomegaly. Phenotyping of B-cell subpopulations confirmed a severe reduction of switched memory B cells in most of the patients that was associated with a higher risk for splenomegaly and granulomatous disease. An expansion of CD21 low B cells marked patients with splenomegaly. Lymphadenopathy was significantly linked with transitional B-cell expansion. Based on these findings and pathogenic consideration of B-cell differentiation, we suggest an improved classification for CVID (EUROclass), separating patients with nearly absent B cells (less than 1%), severely reduced switched memory B cells (less than 2%), and expansion of transitional (more than 9%) or CD21 low B cells (more than 10%). Whereas the first group contains all patients with severe defects of early B-cell differentiation, severely reduced switched memory B cells indicate a defective germinal center development as found in inducible costimulator (ICOS) or CD40L deficiency. The underlying defects of expanded transitional or CD21 low B cells remain to be elucidated [29].

- *Genetics*

The CVID is highly heterogeneous both phenotypically and genetically. Unlike many other primary immunodeficiencies, monogenic forms account for only 2-10% of patients with CVID. Genes that have been implicated in monogenic CVID include: ICOS, TNFRSF13B (TACI), TNFRSF13C (BAFFR), LRBA, TNFSF12 (TWEAK), CD19, ILCR2 (CD21), MS4A1 (CD20), TNFRSF7 (CD27), IL21R, CTLA4, PRKCD, PLCG2, NFKB1, NFKB2, PIK3CD, PIK3R1, CD81, VAV1, RAC2, BLK, IKZF1 (IKAROS) and IRF2BP2.

Due to the increasing number of genes identified in CVID, it has become clear that CVID is a global diagnosis and that many of these genetic defects cause distinct disease entities. In addition, evidence is accumulating to show that at least a subgroup of patients with CVID has a complex rather than monogenic inheritance [30,31].

- *Proposal of an Exploration Strategy in Case of Suspicion of CVID*

Patient's personal and family history collection is a very important time, and brings necessary elements such as repeated infections (sinusitis, bronchitis...), history of malignant or autoimmune diseases. Clinical examination searches for lymphoproliferation (splenomegaly, hepatomegaly and peripheral lymph nodes) and signs in favor of an autoimmune or granulomatous disease.

Searching for target organs involvement is a systematic step. Thus, respiratory exploration will be done by functional respiratory exploration and CT scan sections of the sinuses and lungs. The digestive exploration is essential in case of signs of digestive involvement.

When CVID is suspected, the first-line workup will include a blood count, 24-hour proteinuria, IgG, IgA, IgM or at least serum protein electrophoresis. After confirmation of hypogammaglobulinemia, the second-line workup will consist of a quantitative analysis by flow cytometry of B, T and Natural Killer lymphocytes, combined with vaccine response tests. If a patient with recurrent infections has IgA deficiency alone, IgG subclass testing may be done.

A third level of exploration is conducted by reference centres, such as the switched (CD27+IgD-IgM-) and unswitched (CD27+IgD+IgM+) memory B cells assays and other subgroups of B lymphocytes such as CD21 low. Genetic analysis remains optional, it is not recommended to do it systematically, it is performed usually by research centres.

Currently we are doing a classification study based on B lymphocyte to better explore this disease

III. CONCLUSION

CVID is a heterogeneous syndrome, mainly due to a deficiency of antibodies, which is easy to diagnose and explore if one follows a methodical diagnostic approach. In the majority of cases, the disease is polygenic and multifactorial. Several trials have been attempted to classify CVID into several subgroups according to characteristic clinical and immunological criteria, using flow cytometry and functional B-cell memory assay. Different groups were identified and appear to have different clinical expression and prognosis, which would probably allow future management to be tailored for each of these groups. A comprehensive and more precise approach to classify CVID by combining clinical-immunological and genetic data is being investigated.

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Table 1 Serum contraction values of IgG, IgA and IgM determined by nephelometry

	IgA	IgG	IgM
1-5 Days	0.07-0.22	7.00-13.00	0.04-0.20
5-10 Days	0.07-0.22	6.30-11.50	0.10-0.30
15-30 Days	0.10-0.30	4.60-8.60	0.20-0.65
1-6 mouths	0.10-0.62	3.00-4.50	0.30-0.80
6-12 mouths	0.30-0.86	2.80-5.50	0.40-1.20
1-3 years	0.40-1.22	4.50-8.00	0.50-1.50
3-7 years	0.45-1.50	5.30-10.00	0.50-1.50
7-10 years	0.50-1.60	6.00-12.00	0.50-1.5
10-12 years	0.60-2.00	6.30-12.00	0.50-1.50
Adult M (Men)	0.75-3.50	6.75-12.80	0.50-1.5
Adult W (Women)	0.70-2.60	6.70-12.35	0.70-1.50

Table 2 Value of serum contractions of IgG subclasses

Age (years)	1-1.9	2-2.9	3.3.9	4-5.9	6-7.9	8-9.9	10-12.9	13-17	Adults
IgG1	3.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
IgG2	0.30	0.30	0.35	0.40	0.45	0.50	0.50	0.60	0.60
IgG3	0.12	0.13	0.15	0.16	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17

Table 3 Hypogammaglobulinemia Associated with Hypoalbuminemia

Hypoalbuminemia(permanent ortransient)	Normal Albuminemia
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Nephrotic syndrome - Exudative enteropathy - Paroxysmal capillary leakage -Acute Infectious Episode overlap -Prolonged inflammatory state possible - Undernutrition 	<p>Primary Immune Deficiencies Lymphatic haemopathies Immunosuppressive treatments</p>

** Cause of hypoalbuminemia in a patient already carrying Hypogammaglobulinemia

Table 4 Major causes of Hypogammaglobulinemia to be Excluded at the Time of Diagnosis of an CVID

<p>Agammaglobulinemia:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - X-linked: BTK gene mutation (Bruton) - Autosomal: gene mutation λ 5 <p>From the heavy chain gene μ from Ig</p> <p>From the CD79a gene</p> <p>From the BLNK gene</p>
<p>Purtilo's syndrome (SAP mutation)</p>
<p>Hyper IgM syndrome</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - X-linked (CD154 gene mutation) - Autosomal (cytidine deaminase)
<p>DIPs associated with growth hormone deficiency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Probably heterogeneous group
<p>Severe combined deficits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adenosine deaminase deficiency - Purine phosphorylase deficiency - Gene mutation Υc (X-linked) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - JAK3 gene mutation - Mutation of chain a of the IL7 receiver - Ommen Syndrome (RAG1/RAG2 gene mutation)

Table 5 PAGID/EGID Criteria for Making the Diagnosis of CVID

<p><u>Au moins un des critères suivants :</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -sensibilité accrue aux infections -manifestations autoimmunes -maladie granulomateuse -prolifération polyclonale inexpliquée - antécédent familial de déficit en immunoglobulines
<p>ET</p> <p>Diminution marquée du taux d'IgG et d'IgA (<2 DS) avec ou sans diminution du taux d'IgM</p>
<p>ET</p> <p><u>Au moins un des critères suivants :</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - défaut de réponses vaccinales ou absence d'isohémagglutinines - déficit en cellules B mémoires switchées (< 70 % de la normale pour l'âge)
<p>ET</p> <p>Exclusion des causes secondaires d'hypogammaglobulinémie</p>
<p>ET</p> <p>Diagnostic porté après l'âge de 4 ans</p>
<p>ET</p> <p>Absence de défaut T profond défini par deux des trois critères suivants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CD4 < 200/mm³ - CD4 naïves < 10% des lymphocytes T - Prolifération T absente aux mitogènes et aux antigènes

Fig 1 Serum Protein Electrophoresis Showing Hypogammaglobulinemia